

Action Plan

Towards FAIR Implementation in the Dutch Social Sciences and Humanities

FAIRification reduces costs, boosts innovation, supports informed consent, and strengthens societal trust in research. Although many organisations endorse the FAIR principles, gaps between policy and practice in the SSH stem from technical limits and weak organisational support. The Action Plan for FAIR Implementation tackles these real-world challenges by identifying bottlenecks and proposing practical steps.

Bottleneck

Recommendations

Action

1. FAIR roles and responsibilities are unclear and uneven across institutions, leading to misalignment, gaps, and resistance - especially in small organisations

- Design a blueprint of RDM roles & tasks
- Establish participatory and transparent governance framework for RDM

Map

Untangle FAIR roles and processes

2. Disconnected RDM systems and DMPs treated as paperwork leave researchers unequipped and create repeated effort, inconsistencies, and risks to data quality

- Revise DMPs process
- Build more robust FAIR-enabling digital environments

Equip

Enable FAIR-by-design RDM at RPOs

3. Researchers and managers see little incentive to invest in FAIR, as data and software outputs receive minimal recognition compared to publications

- Integrate FAIR into institutional leadership priorities
- Value FAIR contributions as research outputs

Reward

Make FAIR Count

4. FAIR skills remain uneven across roles, with misconceptions, privacy concerns, and fragmented training preventing effective and confident implementation

- Create FAIR and RDM module for Bachelor and Master's courses
- Organise bring-your-own-(meta)data events

Train

Make FAIR tangible to (future) data providers

5. Professionals struggle to keep up with evolving FAIR practices due to siloed communication, scarce capacity, and limited SSH-specific exchange

- Build shared expert capacity for smaller and resource-limited institutes
- Create SSH FAIR Ambassadors program

Share

Foster knowledge exchange on FAIR

